

NOTES

Preparation of Molybdenum Trisulphide by Solid State Interaction between Molybdenum Trioxide and Thiourea

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MOLYBDENUM trisulphide serves as a high density cathode material in alkali metal cells¹⁻³. It can be converted to very pure molybdenum disulphide which is used as a solid lubricating material in nuclear reactors⁴. The present paper describes a solid state reaction between molybdenum trioxide and thiourea at elevated temperature. The mole ratio of the mixture and the temperature at which the reaction is stoichiometric have been investigated.

Results and Discussion

Change of colour of the reaction mixtures of molybdenum trioxide and thiourea kept at 80° and above from yellow to brown indicated the occurrence of chemical reaction, the extent of which could be seen from Table 1. No reaction occurred below 80° and that decomposition of the reaction product took place above 120°. The amounts of MoS₃ were 43.5, 52.48, 63.49, 76.50 and 99.98% of the theoretical amounts at 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120°, respectively. Increase of proportion of thiourea increased the yield of MoS₃ with the increase of temperature in each system. Optimum amounts were obtained in the MoO₃ - thiourea 1 : 3 system at 120°. This indicated the 1 : 3 stoichiometry of

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF MoS₃ OBTAINED BY THE INTERACTION BETWEEN MoO₃ AND CS(NH₂)₂

Temp. °C	Mole ratio of MoO ₃ (1.4394 g) to CS(NH ₂) ₂						
	1 : 0.5	1 : 1	1 : 1.5	1 : 2	1 : 2.5	1 : 2.75	1 : 3
80	0.051 4	0.128 0	0.235 2	0.364 8	0.520 0	0.677 6	0.835 2
90	0.059 8	0.152 0	0.283 2	0.441 6	0.640 0	0.818 4	1.008 0
100	0.646 4	0.179 2	0.840 8	0.597 6	0.800 0	0.994 4	1.219 2
110	0.080 2	0.218 0	0.408 0	0.659 2	0.984 0	1.214 4	1.468 8
120	0.099 2	0.256 0	0.528 0	0.825 6	1.280 0	1.672 0	1.919 6

Experimental

A series of mixtures containing MoO₃ and CS(NH₂)₂ (both AnalaR) in the mole ratios 1 : 0.50, 1 : 1, 1 : 1.5, 1 : 2, 1 : 2.5, 1 : 2.75 and 1 : 3 were prepared by intimately mixing MoO₃ (0.01 mol, 1.4394 g) with calculated amounts of CS(NH₂)₂. The mixtures were taken in glass stoppered pyrex tubes and were kept at 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110 and 120° (±1°) for 1 h while agitating for a number of times.

To evaluate the extent of the reaction, the mixtures were leached with a dilute solution of (NH₄)₂S which dissolved MoS₃ leaving behind other materials in the residue. The solutions were filtered and the amount of MoS₃ (Table 1) were determined by estimating molybdenum colorimetrically⁵. The residues were treated with hot water, filtered and urea in the filtrates estimated by urease method⁶ employing methyl purple as indicator. The insoluble unreacted MoO₃ was dried in an air-oven and weighed.

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Complexes of Manganese(II) with 2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole

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2-(2'-Pyridyl)benzthiazole (PBT) contains interesting donor sites (N=C-C=N) similar to 2-(2'-pyridyl)benzimidazole and 2,2'-dipyridyl and forms

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